

WHAT WE NEED TO KNOW ABOUT THE PATHOLOGY OF CARDIOMYOPATHY

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Relevance of the problem: according to the WHO definition, cardiomyopathies are heart pathologies resulting in damage to the heart muscle in the myocardium, the middle part of the heart muscle fibers. The disease can appear against the background of other diseases not related to the heart and cardiovascular system.

Presentation and methods: Cardiomyopathy code is ICD 10 according to the International Classification of Diseases. The concept unites all pathologies in which the middle layer of the muscle fibers of the heart is affected. The risk of developing hypertension, coronary heart disease (CHD), and heart valve damage remains high.

In this case, it is recommended to study not all heart pathologies, but symptoms with changes in the myocardium in cardiomyopathy. These disorders can be caused by disorders of individual organs and systems, as well as the whole organism.

Observed results: According to the modern classification, cardiomyopathies can be divided into two main types and several characteristic groups. As mentioned above, the disease can appear by itself or as a result of other diseases. In the first case, the causes are often not identified and cannot be determined using traditional diagnostic methods.

Primary cardiomyopathy can be caused by a viral infection, autoimmune disease, or idiopathic myocardial fibrosis. The reason for this may also be some types of changes in the human genome. It is impossible to determine the influence of the genetic factor on the occurrence of cardiac cardiomyopathy, because a large number of proteins are involved in the metabolism of cardiomyocytes. In this case, the pathology develops only when one or more changes appear.

Symptoms characteristic of cardiomyopathy are caused by viral causes of the development of myopathy. This theory can be confirmed by antibodies detected in connection with the penetration of viruses. For example, the immune system affects the cytomegalovirus, the causative

agent of hepatitis C, as well as the Coxsackie virus. All these pathogens are able to affect DNA, with subsequent development of heart muscle pathology.

According to clinical recommendations, the theory of the development of cardiomyopathy as a result of autoimmune changes in the body is not unreasonable. The mechanism of development is related to the recognition of myocardial cells as foreign by the human immune system. In this case, the body produces antibodies directed against cardiomyocytes. This opposite effect of immunity can be caused by viruses, bacteria and various pathologies.

The restrictive form is characterized by the stiffness of the myocardium with the limitation of filling the heart chambers with blood. A decrease in the volume of blood flow leads to the development of diastolic dysfunction, against which heart failure occurs with the manifestation of acute restrictive cardiomyopathy.

The reason for this may be idiopathic myocardial fibrosis, cardiosclerosis, in which cardiomyopathy appears, the diagnosis indicates the replacement of the characteristic muscle fibers of the heart with connective tissue. They lose elasticity, are unable to contract and disrupt the heart rhythm. The reason for this may be inflammatory processes in the myocardium or a previous heart attack. In this case, what is called secondary cardiomyopathy appears.

How is the treatment carried out?

Due to the uncertain nature of the appearance of the primary form of the disease, treatment is prescribed to weaken and eliminate symptoms. The applied therapy is carried out to eliminate the symptoms of heart failure caused by pathological processes in the myocardium.

What pathologies can cause the secondary form?

Secondary cardiomyopathy appears against the background of pathologies related to the functioning of the human cardiovascular system.

The list of these diseases includes:

IHD, coronary heart disease;

Infections that cause fatal changes in the heart muscle;

Endocrine diseases;

Arterial hypertension;

Shifts in metabolism and accumulation;

Electrolyte balance

In connecting fibers;

amyloidosis;

Neuromuscular pathology;

Severe poisoning;

During pregnancy.

Coronary heart disease is characterized by a number of characteristic symptoms. Against the background of atherosclerosis, the lumen of the coronary arteries narrows and a lack of oxygen (O₂) occurs in the myocardium. This leads to the destruction of cardiomyocytes and their replacement by connective fibers.

Conclusion: Considering the causes of cardiomyopathies, we can distinguish different types of this disease:

Primary origin, when the etiology of occurrence is not determined;

Secondary form with the identification of the cause of the development of pathological changes in the myocardium.

Classification is also carried out according to the mechanism of development, pathogenesis:

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